

SMART AND FLEXIBLE HEAT & POWER FROM FAST PYROLYSIS OIL

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ABSTRACT: Small scale biomass-based Combined Heat and Power (CHP) has the potential to contribute significantly in solving the challenges Europe faces while pursuing the goal to make its energy system smart, clean, flexible, secure, cost competitive and efficient. The overall objective of the SmartCHP project is the realization of a cost-effective and flexible energy system by using Fast Pyrolysis Bio-Oil (FPBO) in an efficient CHP based on a compression-ignition engine. Fast pyrolysis is a process to convert a variety of biomass resources into a uniform liquid fuel called FPBO, nowadays, produced on a commercial scale in Europe. (e.g. Finland, Sweden & the Netherlands). The FPBO originates from different types of lignocellulosic biomasses and/or residues. Two compression-ignition engines are available at BTG, a one-cylinder research engine (1C) and a 48 kW_e, four-cylinder prototype (4C). Both engines have been modified to enable operation on FPBO. The 1C engine has been tested on FPBOs of different origin like e.g., FPBO from sawdust, olive residue, miscanthus as well as with reference fuels like diesel, ethanol, butanol and HVO. Generally, CO emissions were higher with FPBO and NO_x emissions were lower. The overall electrical efficiency was rather similar for all fuels. A catalytic flue gas treatment unit has been installed, and emissions are below current EU regulations. Long duration testing has been part of the work, and over 1,000 operating hours have been accumulated without changing fuel injector and/or fuel pump. The modifications on the 4C prototype are very similar to the 1C engine, and the fuel injection system is even identical. Initial testing of the prototype on FPBO was successful, and results are comparable to the 1C engine. Furthermore, electrical efficiency is hardly dependent on the fuel used. Recently, the flue gas treatment unit has been added to the prototype and commissioning and testing will start soon.

Keywords: pyrolysis oil, CHP, bioenergy, internal combustion engine, renewable energies

1 INTRODUCTION

Small scale biomass-based Combined Heat and Power (CHP) has the potential to contribute significantly in solving the challenges Europe faces while pursuing the goal to make its energy system smart, clean, flexible, secure, cost competitive and efficient. Furthermore, CHP can play an important role in securing electricity supply by balancing a Renewable Energy Sources (RES) based grid (“dispatchable power”) to compensate for fluctuating wind and solar electricity. For small-scale biomass CHP systems, a standardized fuel, enabling optimization of the conversion units and thus creating a cost competitive value chain, is highly preferred. A smart, demand driven unit should be capable of dealing with the fluctuating energy demand and/or varying availability of wind/solar power. In such a case, it is advantageous to use a sustainable liquid fuel and such concept is being demonstrated in the EC-Horizon project SmartCHP.

2 SmartCHP™

2.1 The concept

The overall objective of SmartCHP™ is the realization of a cost-effective and flexible energy system by using Fast Pyrolysis Bio-Oil (FPBO) in an efficient diesel engine based CHP. Fast pyrolysis is a process to convert a variety of biomass resources into a uniform liquid fuel called FPBO, nowadays, produced on a commercial scale in Europe. (e.g. in Finland, Sweden & the Netherlands).

The technical concept of the SmartCHP is outlined in Fig. 1. It combines a FPBO fuelled engine and flue gas boiler to produce electricity and heat at a high efficiency over the whole load range. The approach to achieve the project objective is to integrate the engine, combustor and

flue gas treatment system into a single unit and perform overall system testing and evaluation for a wide range of heat and power output ratios.

An alternative operation approach is to run the engine at higher load and use the excess electricity to produce extra heat via electrical heaters or connecting a heat pump.

2.2 The challenge

Combustion of FPBO in stationary diesel engines is an interesting approach for combined heat & power (CHP) applications. Even at relatively small scale (< 1 MWe) high electrical efficiencies are achievable as well as fast load changes. However, the properties of FPBO make the direct application in engines very challenging. FPBO is acidic, contains water, has a high viscosity (compared to diesel), is sensitive to polymerization and difficult to ignite. Standard fuel injectors and fuel pumps are not corrosion resistant, and these parts will quickly corrode when contacted with FPBO. Stainless steel can withstand corrosion but is often not hard enough to withstand abrasive wear and high impact.

The Cetane Number (CN) of a fuel is important for a compression-ignition engine, and it is inversely related to the fuel's ignition delay. A high value means easy ignition, and typical values for conventional diesel fuels are in the range of 45 to 55. It is hard to find any data on the CN of FPBO, but certainly it is much lower than for diesel. Maximum values reported are around 20 to 25, but also values as low as 4 are published. To compensate for the poor ignition of FPBO a higher temperature at the end of compression is needed. This can be achieved by either increasing the air inlet temperature or by increasing the compression ratio or a combination thereof. The addition of Cetane improvers to the FPBO proved to be inadequate.

Figure 1: The SmartCHP[®] - concept

3 EXPERIMENTAL FACILITIES

Two compression-ignition engines are available at BTG, a one-cylinder research engine (1C) and a 48 kW_e, four-cylinder prototype (4C). Both engines were supplied by ABATO and have been jointly modified to enable operation on FPBO. Modifications include a.o. a corrosion resistant fuel supply, a redesigned fuel injector & pump, increased compression ratio and dedicated engine control software.

The basis for both units is a Weichai 226B engine. The original engine of the 1C test unit is a 3-cylinder engine, but two cylinders have been made inactive. An overview of both systems is given in Table 1.

A more detailed description of the complete set-up's, measurements and operation has been previously published [2,3,4]. More recently, a flue gas treatment system has been added to both test units, which consists of a particle filter, oxidation catalyst and a catalytic DeNO_x unit (SCR). The flue gas treatment including the control unit has been provided by TEHAG in the framework of the European SmartCHP project.

Exhaust gas emissions are measured by a TESTO-350 analyzer (CO, O₂, NO, NO₂, SO_x, H₂S), a Brain-Bee AGS-200 analyzer (CO, HC, NO, O₂) and a Brain-Bee OPTA 800 (opacity measurement for soot). The latter one is only used in the 4C set-up.

Table I: Engine characteristics

	1C set-up	4C - prototype
Engine output	30 kW (~10 kW)	48 kW
Bore & Stroke	105 x 120	105 x 130
Engine speed (rpm)	1,500	1,500
Air intake	Atmospheric	Turbo-charged
Air preheating	Electrical	Heat exchanger (air-flue gas)
Compression ratio	15.5:1 (standard) 17.6:1 (mod.)	18:1 (standard) 22:1 (modified)
Cylinder number	1 (2 of 3 have been made inactive)	4
Fuel system	Mechanical pump	Mechanical pump
Fuel injection pressure (bar)	250 - 350	250 - 350
Generator	Linz SLT18 MD	Xingnuo, XN224E

4 RESULTS

The IC engine has been tested on FPBOs of different origin like e.g., from sawdust, olive residue, miscanthus. In the past at least 20 wt% of ethanol was added to the FPBO to reduce viscosity and improve homogeneity resulting in easier operation. Current experiments were also performed with lower amounts of ethanol or even without any addition. Flue gas emissions are measured, and fuel consumption is determined. An important aspect is also the long-term duration of the engine.

A more scientific analysis of FPBO combustion was performed by Technical University of Eindhoven (TUE) in a so-called Combustion Research Unit (CRU) [5,6]. Moreover, TUE carried out a range of experiments on the IC engine at BTG to gain a better understanding of the engine performance on FPBO. Results of their work will be published soon [7].

4.1 FPBO fuels from different types of biomass

Fast pyrolysis is a suitable process to convert a variety of biomasses and waste streams into a liquid. The actual ‘quality’ will depend on actual feedstock. Here, quality means viscosity, water content and impurities. Besides FPBOs several fuels have been tested for comparison including fossil diesel, ethanol, butanol and HVO (hydrotreated vegetable oil, known as Neste My Renewable Diesel available at fueling stations).

FPBOs from pellet crumbles (Empyro), sawdust (GFN Finland), Miscanthus (BTG) and Olive (BTG, feedstock provided by CAPAX). In all cases 20 wt% of ethanol was added to the FPBO, but GFN-FPBO was also tested without ethanol (GFN₀ or GFN-pure).

Table II: Fuel properties

Fuel	LHV MJ/kg	Water wt%	Acidity mg KOH/g	Density kg/L	Visc. cSt (40°C)
<i>Fast Pyrolysis Oils</i>					
GFN ₀	16.3	20.8	74	1.20	41
GFN ₂₀	18.4	16.2	50	1.11	15
EMP ₂₀	17.9	21.7	51	1.09	12
MISC ₂₀	18.9	16.2	51	1.05	12
Olive ₂₀	19.9	18.8	69	1.04	13
<i>Reference fuels</i>					
Diesel	43.7	-	-	0.824	2.6
EtOH	25.2	2.5	-	0.797	1.2
BuOH	32.8	1.0	-	0.815	2.4
HVO	45.0	-	-	0.770	3.1

The evaluation of experiments is primarily based on a comparison of engine performance using the different fuels (see Table 2). The CO and NOx emissions are shown in Fig. 2 and the relative fuel consumption on mass and energy basis in Fig. 3.

Compared to the reference fuels FPBO leads to a somewhat higher CO and lower NOx emission. The diesel fuel consumption has been taken as the reference, and fuel consumption of other fuels are relative to that value. On a mass basis the fuel consumption is higher for FPBOs but that’s due to the lower gravimetric energy density. Heating values for the different fuels are calculated based on the elemental composition. Fig. 3 shows that on an energy basis the differences are rather small considering that the determination of LHVs is sensitive to small deviations in elemental composition as

well as the type of fuel. In all cases the FPBO fuels consume less fuel on energy basis.

In Fig. 4 the fuel consumption is given as a function of LHV of the fuel, and as expected an inversely proportional relation is observed. The dotted line represents -assuming a constant efficiency at a certain load- this relation according to the equation:

$$\text{Fuel consumption} = \text{constant}/\text{LHV}$$

The experimental data points of the FPBOs are found just below the dotted line, which also shows a slightly higher efficiency for the FPBOs. This is certainly an unexpected result, but likely the engine is not at the optimal setpoint for diesel/HVO.

Figure 2: CO and NO_x content in the exhaust gas for different fuels. Engine load = 1.6 kW_e; T_{air} = 115 °C.

Figure 3: Relative fuel consumption of different fuels. Reference is conventional diesel. Engine load = 1.6 kW_e; T_{air} = 115 °C.

Figure 4: Fuel consumption as a function of the lower heating value (LHV) of the fuel. Engine load = 1.6 kW_e; T_{air} = 115 °C.

4.2 Long duration testing

Long duration testing of an engine running on FPBO is of utmost importance. In most published work the actual operational hours are limited to a few hours or in

the best-case tens of hours. In previous work BTG accumulated almost a thousand running hour of a FPBO fuelled engine, but it required frequent replacement of the fuel pump and/or injector. The longest run was just above 100 hours. An important milestone set for SmartCHP was to achieve at least 500 hours of operation without changing the fuel injection system.

4.2.1 Duration test with FPBO₁₀

The fuel injector used for commissioning and performance testing described in the previous paragraph was used to continue with the duration test. Prior to starting this duration test the injector was already used for about 178h. The duration test was carried out with an air inlet temperature of 135 °C, a load of 1.6 kW_e and FPBO produced by GFN from sawdust.

Figure 5: Exhaust gas temperature as a function of runtime

Based on previous experience it is known that the exhaust gas temperature is a good and fast indication on changes in engine performance. An increasing flue gas temperature means less efficient combustion due to for example wear of injector holes. Fig. 5 shows the exhaust temperature during the 500h run. Overall, only a very slight increase could be observed. During this long-term experiment the SmartCHP milestone (500h operation) was achieved. In Fig. 6 the CO and NO_x emissions are shown for the same experiment. Some fluctuations in measured values are observed, but over the whole period the changes are small. In case of severe injector wear (e.g. increasing hole size, leakage etc) the CO would strongly increase and NO_x would decrease; this trend was certainly not observed.

Figure 6: CO and NO_x concentration in the exhaust gas as a function of runtime. Fuel = GFN₁₀

During the 500h run two emergency stops took place. In both cases erroneous reading of a thermocouple (broken wire/poor connection) caused the emergency stop. The

longest run without any interruption was 333 h (~2 weeks).

4.2.2 Duration testing with pure FPBO

After the run of 500h on GFN₁₀ it was decided to continue for a couple of days on pure FPBO as this would be the ultimate goal (i.e. no addition of ethanol). Therefore, testing was continued at the same conditions with GFN₀.

The experiment with pure FPBO lasted 3 days (as planned). Measurements only took place during the working day and that's the reason for the large intervals between a series of measurements. The exhaust gas temperature was also fairly constant over these 3 days. However, in Fig. 7a trend can be observed of increasing CO concentration and decreasing NO_x content. This could be an indication that some wear occurs, but more likely it is due to fouling. No visual wear was observed on the fuel pump and injector after the duration test.

Figure 7: CO and NO_x concentration in the exhaust gas as a function of runtime. Fuel = GFN₀

4.3 Flue gas treatment

The flue gas treatment system has been provided by TEHAG Germany. It consists of a combined filter-oxidation reactor to reduce CO, HC and PM followed by a SCR reactor to reduce NO_x. Before the SCR reactor AdBlue is injected. The engine was operated at a load of 2 kW_e, and FPBO₁₀ was used as fuel. The average inlet concentration during this test was 348 mg/Nm³ CO, and 1,672 mg/Nm³ NO_x (@15% O₂). A test of around 150h showed stable and high conversion of CO and NO_x, see Fig. 8.

Figure 8: Conversion of CO and NO_x after flue gas treatment. Fuel = GFN₁₀

In Table 3 a comparison is given with existing regulation in Europe and the Netherlands. The values are fairly low, but likely the flue gas treatment system is somewhat overdimensioned for the small test engine.

Meanwhile, a flue gas treatment system is also implemented on the 4C prototype, and tests will be performed in the near future.

Table III: Emissions after flue gas treatment and comparison with existing regulation (mg/Nm³ @ at 15% O₂).

Component	Exp.	EU	NL
CO	18 - 56	-	-
NO _x (as NO ₂)	43 – 80	190	150
SO _x	0	120	65
PM	n.d.	20	20

4.4 Prototype testing

The modifications to the 4C prototype were very similar to the ones implemented on the 1C engine. One difference concerns the air preheating: on the 1C engine an electrical air heater is installed, whereas in the prototype a “air-exhaust gas heat exchanger” has been implemented. The temperature is controlled by controlling the amount of air flowing through the heat exchanger, and a fixed air inlet temperature is obtained under all load conditions. The flue gas treatment system has been installed, but not yet commissioned.

The FPBO used in the 4C tests was produced by Pyrocell (Sweden). Prior to use, the oil is filtrated (40µm) and 10 wt% ethanol has been added (properties, see Table 4).

Table IV: Properties of FPBO used in the prototype testing. (FPBO produced by Pyrocell, Sweden, 10wt% EtOH added).

Property	value	unit
Water content	16.8	wt%
Ash Content	0.00	wt%
Solids Content	0.03	wt%
Density	1.12	kg/L
Acid Number	47.3	mg KOH/g
Carbon residue	14.2	wt%
Kinematic viscosity		
20 °C	42.2	cSt
40 °C	15.1	cSt
50 °C	9.9	cSt
HHV	21.1	MJ/kg
LHV	19.2	MJ/kg

Figure 9: NO_x content in the exhaust gas (before flue gas treatment) as a function of engine load for diesel and FPBO. T_{air} = 125 °C;

Figure 10: CO content in the exhaust gas (before flue gas treatment) as a function of engine load for diesel and FPBO. T_{air} = 125 °C;

In Fig. 9 the NO_x emissions are given as a function of load. Generally, NO_x is lower when FPBO is used as fuel, and also the maximum NO_x concentration is achieved at lower load. Contrary to the experiments with the 1C-engine, the CO emissions are almost the same for diesel and FPBO, see Fig. 10. The maximum load was limited to around 90%, further increase the load led to unstable engine operation.

Figure 11: Exhaust gas opacity as a function of load for diesel and FPBO.

Figure 12: Electrical efficiency as a function of engine load for FPBO and diesel. T_{air} = 125 °C. (LHV_{FPBO} = 19.2 MJ/kg, LHV_{diesel} = 43 MJ/kg).

In Fig. 11 the opacity of the exhaust gas is shown for FPBO and diesel as a function of load. There is no direct relation between opacity and particle emission, but generally low “opacity values” are an indicator for low particle emissions. (for example, black smoke would lead to very high opacity values). However, the sensitivity of the opacity measurement might be quite low for very small particles. Unexpectedly, in the experiments always lower values were observed for FPBO compared to diesel under the same engine operating conditions. This might be due to the fact that the test engine settings are not optimized for the use of diesel.

In Fig 12 the electrical efficiency is shown as a function of the engine load. Similar to the IC engine the efficiencies for FPBO and diesel are very similar.

5 CONCLUSIONS

Two engines have been successfully modified to enable FPBO as the fuel: a 1-cylinder research engine and a 4-cylinder, 48 kW_e prototype. The performances of the engines have been characterized by a set of experiments such as changing loads, variations in air inlet temperatures, type of fuels -including reference fuels-, ethanol content in FPBOs and long duration testing.

Generally, FPBOs result in higher CO emissions and lower NO_x compared to the reference fuels. However, in all cases a flue gas treatment system will be needed to comply with emission regulation. Due to the relatively low heating value of FPBO more fuel must be fed compared to e.g. diesel, but on an energy basis almost similar values are obtained.

An important project milestone was achieved by demonstrating 500h engine operation without changing the fuel injection system.

6 REFERENCES

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7 ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

Financial support from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme (Grant Agreement No 815259 – SmartCHP) is gratefully acknowledged.

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